
**CULTURAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND ITS INFLUENCE ON
LOCAL PEOPLE**

Nuriddinova Gulsanam Najmiddin qizi

Student, Economy faculty

“TIAME” National Research University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Scientific adviser: Yuldasheva Nargiza Abdukholiq qizi

Teacher, English Department

“TIAME” National Research University,

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotation: The main purpose of this scientific work to analyze important aspects of cultural tourism and its impact on local communities. In this research it is also studied that appealing tourists to a certain place with creation and development of cultural attractions makes local people's living conditions better.

Key words: cultural tourism, local communities, cultural attractions, tourists

**РАЗВИТИЕ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА
МЕСТНОЕ НАСЕЛЕНИЕ**

Нуриддинова Гульсанам Наджмиддин кызы

Студент экономического факультета

Национальный исследовательский университет «ТИИМСЭ», Ташкент,
Узбекистан

Научный руководитель: Юлдашева Наргиза Абдухолик кызы

Преподаватель кафедры английского языка

«ТИИМСЭ» Национальный исследовательский университет, Ташкент,
Узбекистан

Аннотация: Основная цель данной научной работы проанализировать важные аспекты культурного туризма и его влияние на местные сообщества.

В данном исследовании также изучается, что привлечение туристов в определенное место с созданием и развитием культурных достопримечательностей улучшает условия жизни местного населения.

Ключевые слова: культурный туризм, местные сообщества, культурные достопримечательности, туристы.

***MADANIY TURIZMNING RIVOJLANISHI VA UNING MAHALLIY
AHOLIGA TA'SIRI***

Nuriddinova Gulsanam Najmiddin qizi

Talaba, Iqtisodiyot fakulteti

“ТИИМЕ” Milliy tadqiqot universiteti, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

Ilmiy maslahatchi: Yuldasheva Nargiza Abduxoliq qizi

Ingliz tili bo‘limi o‘qituvchisi

“ТИИМЕ” Milliy tadqiqot universiteti, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy ishning asosiy maqsadi madaniy turizmning muhim jihatlari va uning mahalliy hamjamiyatlarga ta'sirini tahlil qilish. Ushbu tadqiqotda, shuningdek, madaniy diqqatga sazovor joylarni yaratish va rivojlantirish orqali turistlarni ma'lum bir joyga jalb qilish mahalliy aholining yashash sharoitlarini yaxshilashi o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy turizm, mahalliy jamoalar, madaniy diqqatga sazovor joylar, turistlar

Cultural tourism is a type of tourism that focuses on experiencing the culture, traditions, history, and lifestyle of a destination. This type of tourism involves visiting cultural sites, museums, art galleries, historical landmarks, festivals, and participating in local activities and traditions. Cultural tourism allows travelers to immerse themselves in the unique characteristics of a place and gain a deeper understanding of its people, customs, and way of life. It can also help to preserve and promote local heritage and traditions, as well as contribute to the local

economy by supporting cultural institutions and businesses. Some popular cultural tourism destinations include cities known for their historical architecture and cultural attractions, as well as regions that are known for their unique traditions, crafts, music, and cuisine. Travelers who engage in cultural tourism often come away with a greater appreciation for diversity and a broader perspective on the world.

In Europe, travelling different places plays a significance role not only in enhancing cultural understanding, but also helps to increase a country's economy. By the 1980s the flow of international tourists to major sites and attractions began to attract enough attention for the label 'cultural tourism' to be attached to an emerging niche market (Greg Richards, 2018).

One of the key benefits of cultural tourism is its potential to boost local economies. Visitors who engage in cultural tourism activities often spend money on accommodations, meals, souvenirs, and entrance fees to cultural attractions. This infusion of tourism dollars can create jobs, support local businesses, and generate revenue for cultural institutions. In many cases, cultural tourism can be a significant driver of economic development in communities that rely on heritage sites and cultural landmarks as tourist attractions.

In addition to its economic benefits, cultural tourism can also have a positive social impact on local communities. By showcasing their cultural heritage to visitors, communities can preserve their traditions, language, arts, and crafts. This exchange of knowledge and cultural understanding can promote intercultural dialogue and foster a sense of pride and identity among residents. Furthermore, cultural tourism can create opportunities for local residents to participate in tourism activities, thus empowering them to showcase their cultural In addition to its economic benefits, cultural tourism can also have a positive social impact on local communities.

Cultural values and traditions and forms of home architecture can be a potential for tourism based on local culture. However, the existence of this local

community can also be a problem due to several factors: the expansion of this national park had eliminated the existence of indigenous communities from arable land that it has long tilled as a source of livelihood there. This condition causes the community to lose their livelihood; the livelihoods of local communities are generally traditional agriculture. The community utilizes forest products, as well as working the land within the forest area in human (fields), rice fields, gardens. Changing habits from livelihoods as farmers to tourism services is not easy (International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 2020). To address the challenges posed by cultural tourism, it is essential to promote sustainable practices that balance economic development with environmental and social considerations. This includes engaging local communities in tourism planning and decision-making, implementing measures to reduce the carbon footprint of tourism activities, and supporting initiatives that conserve and protect cultural heritage sites. By adopting a holistic approach to cultural tourism management, destinations can ensure the long-term viability of their cultural resources while providing meaningful experiences for visitors.

The idea of community development is explored in phrases of participation, empowerment and community capacity as they associated with tourism development (Telfer & Sharpley, 2008).

Community development can be visible as constructing social capital for collective advantages. Community development goals to growth citizens' participation in their community. In community development, emphasis is located on community as a social machine, bounded by way of geographical place or common hobby (Weaver, 2010). community development is connected to community capability constructing through a shared cognizance to a collective participatory force (Williams,

2004). Community development is undertaken to strengthen or construct community courting and give a boost to systems which have become fragmented (Yan, 2004). According to Timothy (2002) community development helps local

community citizens to pick out unmet wishes. It seeks to build ability with the aid of enhancing ability and knowledge for individuals and the community as an entire (Timothy, 2002). Tourism can be a powerful tool for economic development, creating jobs, generating foreign exchange earnings, and diversifying the economy. However, it is important to implement policies and practices that ensure the benefits of tourism are distributed equitably and that negative impacts are minimized. By doing so, countries can harness the potential of tourism to drive sustainable economic development(American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences,2023).

In conclusion, cultural tourism has the potential to enrich the lives of both travelers and local communities by fostering a deeper appreciation for cultural diversity and heritage. By recognizing the economic, social, and environmental impacts of cultural tourism, it will be developed significantly.

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